

REGARDING CERTAIN ISSUES OF THE TRANSPORT
LOGISTICS OF CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: This article highlights some problems in the transport logistics system of the Central Asia countries. These issues have been studied in detail on the example of permits used in international road transport. Additionally, the experience of the European Union in solving these problems has been studied as a solution to these problems, and the issues of its practical implementation considering the economic potential and capability of the region have been examined.

Key words: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Central Asia, permit for international cargo transportation, Chamber of Commerce, Ministry of Transport, TIR Convention, transit to/from a third country.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада Марказий Осиё давлатларининг транспорт-логистикаси тизимидаги айрим муаммолар ёритиб берилган. Мазкур муаммолар автомобиль транспортида халқаро юк ташишда қўлланиладиган рухсатномалар мисолида атрофлича ўрганилган. Шунингдек мазкур муаммоларни ечими сифатида Европа Иттифоқи тажрибаси ўрганилган бўлиб, уни минтақанинг иқтисодий имконияти ва салоҳиятидан келиб чиққан ҳолда амалда тадбиқ этиш масалалари тадқиқ этилган.

Таянч сўзлар: Ўзбекистон, Тожикистон, Қирғизистон, Қозоғистон, Туркменистон, Марказий Осиё, халқаро юк ташиш учун рухсатнома, Божхона қўмитаси, Транспорт вазирлиги, ЕСМТ, ташқи савдо айланмаси, халқаро шартнома, иккитомонлама ташув, учинчи давлатдан/га ташув.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются некоторые проблемы в транспортно-логистической системе стран Центральной Азии. Эти вопросы подробно изучены на примере разрешительных документов, используемых в международных автомобильных перевозках. Также был изучен опыт Европейского Союза как решение этих проблем, и изучены вопросы его практической реализации исходя из экономического потенциала региона.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, Таджикистан, Кыргызстан, Казахстан, Туркменистан, Центральная Азия, разрешение на международные грузоперевозки, Таможенный комитет, Министерство Транспорта, ЕСМТ, внешнеторговый оборот, международные сооглошения, двухсторонние перевозка, перевозки в/из третьих стран.

Introduction

It is known that since Uzbekistan gained independence, it has chosen the Central Asian region as the priority direction of its foreign policy. Especially, if the main issue of cooperation in foreign policy is related to regional security, then it was reflected in economic and social aspects.

In particular, with the initiative of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A.Karimov, on September 8, 2006, the signing of the Semipalatinsk Treaty regarding the establishment of a nuclear-weapon-free zone in Central Asia (Uzbekistan ratified this document on April 2, 2007) was one of the significant steps in this regard [1].

In 2017, with the initiative of President SH.M.Mirziyoyev, the establishment of the Consultative Meeting of the leaders of the Central Asian states marked an important step towards the enhancement of regional cooperation. As part of these efforts, in Nur-Sultan the capital of Kazakhstan in 2018, in Tashkent in 2019, in

“Avaza” national tourist zone of Turkmenistan in 2021, in Cholpon-Ata city of Kyrgyzstan, and in Dushanbe city of Tajikistan, meetings were held in a unique and meaningful manner, with rich content [2].

These political measures have highlighted that the President of Uzbekistan has consistently emphasized issues related to trade, economy, and transportation-logistics in every speech.

Analysis of the Topic-related Literature

In the field of the topic being researched, researchers who have studied the Central Asian countries in a proper manner can be divided into two groups. For instance, scholars in this region, both domestic and foreign, have been engaged in studying various aspects of science and knowledge, primarily due to the necessity of their collaboration in a comprehensive sense, especially from a political standpoint.

If we pay attention to the projects that have been organized towards international purposes, we can see that much more attention has been given to the projects related to transportation, especially in the context of regional and global significance. In particular, M.O.Turaev and S.Kozhemyakin emphasize transport projects as a distinctive feature of the region’s specialization. In their work, international transport projects are cited as the main driving force for the development of the countries.

A.Sechnikov and S.Chaplinsky highlight Central Asia’s economic potential in the context of global processes. In their research, they pay special attention to the transformation of transportation projects in the region in connection with changing geopolitical trends [3].

In the work of O.Podberyozkin, in the Central Asian region, movement to establish the benefits of Russia in Central Asia has been undertaken. It analyzes long-term transportation projects within the territory of the Russian Federation, assesses them from an economic and security perspective, and evaluates projects opposing Russia’s interests [4].

Similarly, American scholar F.Starr, in his academic articles, focuses on the state of the transport system of the Moscow-Tashkent railway and presents a series of ideas for creating new transport corridors. He is also considered the author of the “New Silk Road” strategy adopted by the US government. In addition, he aims to study the state of transportation security of regional states in states in his explorations, particularly focusing on developing the trans-Afghan corridor to enhance security in the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan’s territory [5].

Analysis and Results

The relevance of the topic and the necessity to achieve real practical results are highlighted by bringing up important facts. Specifically, if the Central Asian countries’ share in Uzbekistan’s foreign trade turnover was 12.4% in 2019, 13,6% in 2022, and reached 15.0% in 2022, it indicates the ongoing yearly trends. Along with this, the following numerical table also makes it possible to understand the growth in trade relations among the state sectors.

Table 1

**The volume of trade turnover between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the
Central Asian countries**

(in millions of US dollars)

Countries	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Kazakhstan	2055,8	2919,6	3367,7	3018,5	3910,5	4621,0
Kyrgyzstan	253,7	402,8	829,0	903,2	952,6	1260,0
Tajikistan	237,9	390,5	497,0	501,9	604,5	674,4
Turkmenistan	177,9	302,8	541,9	527,1	881,9	926,3

Despite various challenges, more than 300 agreements and contracts totaling 75 million U.S. dollars have been signed with the aim of achieving practical results

and positive outcomes in the foreign policy of these five Central Asian countries. This includes trade deals worth the equivalent of over 75 billion U.S dollars [6].

In this context, it is possible to observe that the international trade's transportation logistics within the region are sufficiently developed and progressing at a necessary rate.

In particular, in 2015-2017, through border settlements with Afghanistan - 4294, 5808, 9723, respectively, with Turkmenistan - 45724, 46829, 47810, with Tajikistan - 21601, 18214, 23513, with Kyrgyzstan - 9847, 23544, 19017, with Kazakhstan - 61964, 73500, 110853 trucks moved, and the amount of transported cargo increased accordingly.

In particular, in the last three years, 94752, 132600, 216145 tons were transported through the corridor of the Republic to Afghanistan, 913661, 936543, 961322 tons through Turkmenistan, 422253, 358658, 474146 tons through Kyrgyzstan, 198540, 3892 tons through Tajikistan. 13, 392801 tons, with Kazakhstan 1000787, 1340178, 2081939 tons of foreign trade goods were handled. These numbers make up 10-13% of the total foreign trade cargo transportation index (road transportation, railway transportation, river port (the only port of Termez in Uzbekistan) and air landing) on average [7].

Specifically, the movement of international trade goods through road transport within the region's countries is being influenced by documents that grant permission for the transportation of international trade goods through road transport, thus affecting its foreign trade balance. Consequently, there is an increase in excessive expenditures and time consumption for exporting and importing goods for business entities within the region.

All vehicles engaged in movement within the territory of the Republic are subject to the standards set for their dimensions (lengths-12m, for road trains-20m, height-4m, width-2,5m, weight-40tons) and are operated based on Special Permits issued by the Automobile Roads Authority under the State Traffic Safety

Committee, which are derived from established criteria (later referred to as a permit) in case of exceeding the specified criteria.

The procedure for issuing these types of Permits is carried out in accordance with the Resolution No.342 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 2011.

Based on this resolution, individuals who wish to obtain a permit for a cargo vehicle must submit an application to the authorized agency 15 days in advance. The permit is only issued by the central office of the Road Transport Committee. Additional expenses and time are required to obtain a permit for vehicles transporting mail to remote posts offices in Tashkent.

Furthermore, foreign experience shows that according to the Federal Law No. 127 of 1998 in Russia, amendments made on January 1, 2018, allow for the issuance of such Permits in electronic form.

Additionally, each subject of Russia has the authority to issue this document (while in Uzbekistan, it is only issued by the central apparatus of the Automobile Roads Authority). A beneficiary can also obtain the permit through the “Unified Portal of State Services” (www.gosuslugi.ru) in Russia. The website www.rosavtodor.ru provides information on routes and movement possibilities across Russia. In Kazakhstan, a similar procedure is established based on the law. (Website: www.gov4c.kz, www.elicense.kz). Moreover, at present, Uzbekistan possesses dual-sided agreements with neighbouring countries for international cargo transportation via road vehicles.

Through these agreements, the transportation of foreign trade goods using road vehicles is facilitated with the document ‘**Permit for International Cargo Transportation by Road Transport**’ (later referred to as the Permit) which is indicated and executed according to the movement. This document is provided by the authorized agencies of the states that are parties to the agreement and bears a special security feature.

For reference: state agencies with the authority to issue permits and allocate national quotas to carriers: In Uzbekistan – **Uzbekistan Automobile Transport Agency**; in Turkmenistan – **Ministry of Automobile Transport**; in Tajikistan – Ministry of Communications and Transport; in Kyrgyzstan – **Ministry of Communications and Transport**.

The permit is considered as a document (form) that grants the right to carry out transportation according to the specified type of cargo through the state territory by road transport. In practice, permits are mainly issued for three types of transportation: bilateral transportation, transit transportation, and transportation to/from a third country. Each country determines the issuance, allocation of quotas, coordination with other countries, division of permits, and usage regulations for these permits based on its internal regulation.

In particular, on March 15, 2018, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a resolution regarding “**Measures for Further Organizing the International Transportation of Goods and Passengers by Road**”. According to the provisions of this resolution, the process of obtaining a permit document is carried out in 7 stages. The issuance of the document is considered in advance, with the application submitted before (at least three months) the start of the following year.

The main purpose of issuing permits is to safeguard the benefits of each country’s national carriers in the field of logistics from foreign carriers. In other words, it ensures that cargo transport vehicles entering the territories of designated countries adhere to equal conditions for entry and exit based on reciprocity.

In total, the Uzbekistan Automobile Transport Agency, in collaboration with authorized bodies of foreign countries, issued permit documents as follows: 30520 permits in 2015, 29400 permits in 2016, 30930 permits in 2017, and 52249 permit documents in 2018, all in accordance with the principle of equitable rights [8].

Nevertheless, this document serves as an administrative measure to oversee the unrestricted movement of vehicles engaged in international transport according

to regions. Currently, only Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan (Article 4 of the document) have mutual agreements based on a bilateral format to not require this permit document.

Furthermore, by examining the type of transportation of regional countries, it is possible to discern the trajectory of movement of transit goods based on the schedule in the attached table using permit document.

Table 2

Table of comparison of the movement types of permit documents between Uzbekistan and neighbouring countries

	Kazakhstan	Kyrgyzstan	Tajikistan	Turkmenistan
Bilateral	-	-	+	+
From/to a third country	+	+	+	+

(Explanation: in this case, + permits are obtained, - permits are not obtained)

The foreign trade turnover of Uzbekistan with these two countries has been increasing year by year regardless of the cancellations of export permits. In particular, with Kyrgyzstan in 2017 - \$254 million USD, in 2018 - \$402,8 million USD, and in 2022, almost tripling to \$1.26 billion USD. Similarly, in line with this trend, Uzbekistan's overall trade turnover with Kazakhstan, which amounted to \$2919,6 million USD in 2018, reached \$4,621 million USD with a 1,5-fold increase in 2022 [9].

In recent years, despite arriving on the same days, the practice of mutual transit with the states of Tajikistan and Turkmenistan on the basis of permits continues to be maintained in Uzbekistan. As a result of the availability of this administrative opportunity, both countries are demonstrating their positive

influence in the field of external trade and transportation logistics, aiming to effectively enhance their capabilities and potential.

Despite the improving conditions, the challenges posed by the pandemic period and the international cargo transportation issues with the Turkmenistan government are still unresolved.

During the pandemic period, especially from February 2020 to June 1, 2022, if international transportation vehicles on the Uzbek-Turkmen border were temporarily immobilised through the exchange of diplomatic notes, and after the pandemic period, the mutual recognition of the permit document and their collection among Turkmen transport companies is being negotiated, it is expected that international transportation will resume without being used in transit.

Beyond this, in terms of Uzbekistan's international trade relations, the lowest indicator is possessed by the Republic of Tajikistan. The requirement for an authorization document with the republic of Tajikistan is evaluated as a "restrictive measure" in international trade, besides all countries of the Uzbekistan region have international checkpoints for the transportation of goods by automobile, and all border customs posts are operating in a 24/7 mode.

Nevertheless, in terms of international freight transportation between the Central Asian states, integration of regional customs services (or other authorized bodies for transporting international goods) into modern information systems is not implemented in real-time.

These days automated information systems are used in all administrative services of five-member states, operating on a real-time schedule. Specifically, in Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, there are integrated automated information systems; in Kazakhstan, the "Astana-1" and customs management systems; and in Turkmenistan, the foreign trade customs duties are being formalised based on the "ASYCUDA WORLD" information system [10].

(Note: Author's development as a result of research)

Likewise, based on the above model, it is necessary to implement the process of crossing the border points for the official registration of food products and other surveillance authorities of state agencies separately, with the possibility of expedited passage as much as possible. When exporting goods for foreign trade, it is essential to ensure the availability of the following 20 types of information in the documentation.

Table 3

Minimum necessary information for streamlining foreign trade

1.	The complete classified name of the product	11.	State registration number of the cargo carrier (freight transporter/hauler)
2.	Product's HS (Harmonized System) code	12.	State where the cargo carrier is registered
3.	Quantity and number of items in the product's primary packaging unit	13.	Name and full address of the shipping company
4.	Gross weight of the product	14.	Chassis number of the cargo carrier

5.	Net weight of the product	15.	Identification means (seal) number and quantity attached to the cargo
6.	Invoice value of the product in US dollars	16.	Citizenship of the driver
7.	Exporting country	17.	Full name of the driver
8.	Importing country	18.	Passport series and number of the driver
9.	Name and full address of the exporter	19.	Name (SMR, invoice, etc.)
10.	Name and full address of the importer	20.	Container number (if available) used for shipping the cargo

In the above model example, it is possible to illustrate the export of the product “GLASS” from Turkmenistan to Uzbekistan. Specifically, “GLASS” products from a glass factory located in Turkmenistan’s Ahal province are being exported to Uzbekistan’s Bukhara province by road transport for a construction company. This product has been officially approved for export from Turkmenistan’s customs authorities, and relevant information and data are processed in real-time through Uzbekistan’s customs service information systems. After the cargo is shaped, permission to enter Uzbekistan is granted virtually when it has passed a preliminary inspection by the attendant stationed at the entry checkpoint of the customs office, without the cargo having reached the customs office yet.

Furthermore, when glass products leave Turkmenistan’s exit customs office and arrive in Uzbekistan, their actual arrival is confirmed through an information system that identifies the cargo vehicle. Following this confirmation, typically within 2-3 minutes, permission is granted for the cargo to enter the customs office premises, where it will engage in foreign economic activities.

In this process, the heads of state of the respective countries are also striving to organize international events to address the issue of separate lanes (currently, most Uzbekistan border customs checkpoints have four lanes for entry and exit) in the infrastructure of border crossing points of the regional states that have emerged from the infrastructure of border crossing points of the regional states.

Foreign experience indicates that regional cooperation is close in terms of the use of permits in international transportation among a number of states geographically adjacent to each other.

For example, it is possible to observe that the authorities of the states that enter this region in the matter of permits from European countries have come to an agreement.

Specifically, the Council of Ministers of Transport of Europe (CEMT) is currently composed of 43 participating states. National carriers of European countries will carry out freight transportation within the region based on permits named CEMT, which is a comprehensive permit giving legal power among participating countries in the conference.

The national carrier of European countries will carry out cargo transportation within the region based on permits known as CEMT permits. CEMT permits are comprehensive and confer legal authority among participating states in a conference.

This document is provided for the transport of goods not subject to quotas among the European countries, and it is considered a universal permit. The validity period for a single permit is long-term – 1 year, and short-term – 30 days. If a shipping company does not use the document in international transportation within 3 months from the day of obtaining the permit, its validity will be revoked.

For reference:

1. In the Central Asian states, a single permit is issued for the first entry, and for the second entry, movement is required based on a new permit.

2. Permits are mainly issued in the region's countries for the transportation of 6000 goods, primarily for 3000 cargo carriers (two-way, transit, to/from a third country/state), and 3000 passenger carriers.

Through the Republic's territory, it is possible to introduce complexities in the procedures related to the international transit, especially the increase in transit cargoes, which may have a positive impact on the customs clearance of international cargo. In this regard, an electronic ship is installed on vehicles that enter the customs checkpoint, and its movement direction is determined by the customs inspector. The Republic Customs Committee has established a centre for monitoring electronic surveillance, which is equipped with nearly 6000 video surveillance cameras, enabling real-time surveillance of customs checkpoints. With the help of these cameras, video surveillance can be carried out on more than 500 vehicles undergoing customs inspection within the country's borders at any given time.

Conclusion

It is clear that with the aim of improving the logistics of road transport vehicles for the transportation of foreign trade goods of the Central Asian states and taking into account the experience of developed countries, the following measures are being implemented:

1. Establishing government councils, under the authority of agencies responsible for transport within the region, in accordance with the Ministries of State. (Under the auspices of government ministries)
2. Progressing through the stages of obtaining permits in the field of transport within the region, considering national benefits, step by step.
3. To expedite the passage of international cargo through border customs posts of the regional states by establishing a mechanism for exchanging information about foreign trade cargoes with a focus on motor vehicle transport vehicles:

First, to produce a fully automated information system working online among five states.

Second, in order to ensure the reliability, integrity, and speed of information, an administrator with authority in this field is appointed for each state. In this case, every piece of information must be confirmed with an electronic digital signature.

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